

MINERALOGICAL AND HYDRAULIC CHARACTERISATION OF HISTORIC FLOTATION TAILINGS

Todor Angelov

University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; E-mail: tangelov419@gmail.com

ABSTRACT. A composite flotation tailings sample from historic Medet tailings dam was characterised to understand occurrences of copper and hydraulic properties of the material and to determine if there is an economic benefit of its reprocessing using hydrometallurgical processes. Conventional ICP-OES multi-element scan and carbon and sulphur determination by Leco were followed by sequential copper assay and mineralogical analysis using the Tescan Integrated Mineral Analyser (TIMA) to identify the elemental composition, acid soluble copper and mineral abundance and liberation. The tailings sample contained 0.105% Cu, 0.41 % S and 0.05% C. The analysis of the gangue minerals showed that the bulk of the material is made up of plagioclase feldspar with moderate amounts of K-feldspars and small amounts of mica, chlorite and clay minerals. Copper minerals cuprite and chalcopyrite with minor amounts of covellite and bornite were observed in the mineralogical analysis of the sample by TIMA. Based on the sequential copper assays, it was estimated that approximately 59.8% of copper contained in the sample reports as acid soluble copper. To understand the flow behaviour in the material the main hydraulic properties like hydraulic conductivity and moisture retention capacity were determined.

Key words: tailings, copper, minerals, hydraulic properties

Introduction

Waste materials generated during flotation processing of finely ground ore and stored in the historical tailings storage facilities generally contain significant amounts of metals of interest. This is mainly due to some inefficiencies in the existing beneficiation techniques at the time of active operations. However, as primary ores are increasingly degrading and becoming more complex, historical flotation tailings are more frequently regarded as an important alternative source of various metals (Grigorova, 2011; Shengo and Maloba, 2013; Grigorova et al., 2015; Stanković et al., 2018; Babel et al., 2018; Figueiredo et al., 2019; Yankova, 2020).

The Medet Tailings Dam contains copper flotation tailings, generated by the Medet and Assarel operations from 1965 until 1990. It is located near the town of Pirdop in the Sredna Gora Mountain and accommodates approximately 170 million tones of waste material as reported by Sultanov (2001). This study examines if hydrometallurgical reprocessing of the Medet Tailings Dam materials could enable viable copper recovery.

The specific study objectives were to: (1) define physical properties of the materials, like bulk and particle density, particle size and screen characteristics; (2) determine the total copper content and the content of other elements, as well as the overall mineral abundance, copper bearing mineral associations and acid consuming gangue minerals (3) assess leachability of copper in the deposited material and (4) characterise the material hydraulically by saturated hydraulic conductivity and moisture retention determinations. The results from this study were used as a first step in the assessment whether the leaching processes are technically feasible for tailings reprocessing of the Medet Tailings Dam.

Materials and Methods

Sampling

The tailings material with a total weight of approximately 320 kg was sampled from thirteen (13) pits excavated in pre-selected areas of the tailings dam, as given in Figure 1.

Thirteen (13) samples were collected from the pit depth greater than 3 meters to reject the sampling of upper layers material with very low (0.03%) copper content. The samples were designated with the letters from A to M.

Fig.1. Image of the Medet Tailings Dam with the location of sampling points

A composite sample identified as a MT-H was prepared so that each pit sample is properly represented in one overall sample representing the total material collected. The MT-H sub-samples were submitted to Process Mineralogical Consulting Ltd. for elemental and mineral analysis and to GeoSystems Analysis Inc. for hydraulic characterisation.

Sample characterisation

The tailings samples were characterised physically, chemically and mineralogically. These studies included specific gravity and bulk density determination, size analysis, chemical and mineralogical analyses and sequential copper assay.

The bulk density of the material was measured with 100 ml cylindrical vessel of stainless steel and the particle density was determined by the use of water pycnometer. A combined sieve and hydrometer analysis was used to determine the particle size distribution of the tailings material. The elemental analysis was performed by Inductively-Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) multi-element scan, whereas carbon and sulphur were separately analysed with the Leco carbon-sulphur analyser. To identify the mineral abundance, type of the copper bearing minerals, liberation and association, nine (9) polished sections were prepared and each polished section was analysed utilising the Tescan

Integrated Mineral Analyser (TIMA) equipped with widely used scanning electron microscope (Dobrev et al., 2009; Valchanova et al., 2011; Schulz et al., 2020). The amounts of oxide minerals, secondary sulphide minerals, and primary copper minerals were determined using semi-quantitative diagnostic technique, referred as sequential copper assay. The leaching procedure used for the assay was as outlined by Parkinson and Bhappu (1995).

The saturated hydraulic conductivity of the material was determined utilising the standard test method (ASTM D 2434-68, 2006) and the moisture retention characteristic curve was determined using pressure plate extractor (ASTM D6836-16, 2016). A one-dimensional (1-D) consolidation test was performed by GeoSystems Analysis Inc. to determine compression, porosity and estimated height of the tailings material when subjected to an increased loading.

Results and Discussion

Bulk Density and Specific Gravity

The bulk and particle density of the tailings sample were determined as 1.54 g/cm³ and 2.74 g/cm³, respectively.

Size Analysis

The combined sieve and hydrometer analysis on the MT-H sample was conducted by GeoSystems Analysis Inc. to assess the particle size distribution of the material. The P₉₀ and P₅₀ for the MT-H sample were determined to be 0.3 mm and 0.05 mm, respectively. The results are presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Particle Size Distribution

The figure shows that the material contained mainly fine sand, silt and small amounts of clay; thus, it could be classified as a fine-earthed fraction.

Chemical Analysis

The chemical analysis of the tailings material was performed by Process Mineralogical Consulting Ltd. The assayed copper content was 0.105% and the value is consistent with the previous available data, published by Sultanov (2001). The tailings also contained 0.41% S and 0.05% C. The results from ICP-OES and Leco analyses are provided in Table 1. As can be seen from Table 1, the major elements include Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg and Na and minor elements include Ti. The tailings also contain Ba, Cr, Mn, P, Sr and V with concentrations above 100 ppm, and trace elements Mo, Ni and Zn.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of flotation tailings material

Parameter	Unit	Value
Cu	%	0.105
S	%	0.41
C	%	0.05
Ag	ppm	<1
Al	%	4.59
As	ppm	<50
Ba	ppm	514
Be	ppm	<10
Bi	ppm	<20
Ca	%	2.01
Cd	ppm	<10
Co	ppm	<10
Cr	ppm	274
Fe	%	2.31
K	%	3.3
La	ppm	<50
Mg	%	1.02
Mn	ppm	295
Mo	ppm	21
Na	%	1.82
Ni	ppm	12
P	ppm	870
Pb	ppm	<20
Sb	ppm	<50
Sr	ppm	550
Ti	%	0.21
Tl	ppm	<50
V	ppm	186
W	ppm	<50
Zn	ppm	32

Mineralogical Analysis

The prepared polished sections were scanned using TIMA technique by Process Mineralogical Consulting Ltd. to identify the mineral abundance. The resulting mineral list is provided in Table 2 along with the values regarding the abundance of each material.

Table 2. Minerals identified in flotation tailings material

Mineral	Unit	Value
Pyrite	%	0.49
Chalcopyrite	%	0.06
Bornite	%	0.00
Tetrahedrite	%	0.00
Chalcocite	%	0.00
Covellite	%	0.01
Chrysocolla	%	0.0002
Malachite	%	0.0002
Cuprite	%	0.02
Cu-Sulfate	%	0.00
Other Cu	%	0.00
Oxides	%	1.33
Quartz/Feldspar	%	61.2
K-Feldspar	%	20.7
Mica	%	7.84
Clay minerals	%	1.33
Chlorite	%	4.33

Mineral	Unit	Value
Carbonates	%	0.30
Apatite	%	0.41
Other Silicates	%	1.46
Other minerals	%	0.55
Unclassified	%	0.01
Total	%	100

The mineralogical analysis of the material provided a detailed analysis of the gangue minerals present in the sample and showed that much of the material is made up of quartz/feldspar (61.2%), moderate amounts of K-feldspar (20.7%), with lesser amounts of mica (7.84%) and chlorite (4.33%), and minor amounts of clay minerals (1.33%). In addition to the gangue mineralogy, the TIMA results revealed copper distribution by mineral species according to Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Copper distribution by minerals (TIMA image)

The figure shows that copper is mainly present as cuprite and chalcocopyrite with minor amounts present as covellite and bornite. Trace amounts of malachite, chrysocolla, chalcocite and tetrahedrite were also observed contributing to the appearance of copper.

The results from TIMA mineral liberation analysis show the fine nature and the locking character of the grains – Table 3.

Cuprite is present primarily as locked grains, but also shows significant amount as free and liberated grains. Chalcocopyrite remains as locked grains with only minor amounts as free grains, while malachite occurs overall as locked grains.

The majority of the pyrite is present as free and liberated grains, but also contains substantial amount as locked grains with moderate amount as middling grains.

Table 3. TIMA mineral liberation

Liberation	Cuprite	Pyrite	Chalco- pyrite	Malachite
Free	8.57	53.8	3.50	0.00
Liberated	24.2	10.1	0.70	0.00
Middling	4.60	5.99	1.72	0.00
Sub- Middling	0.00	1.37	2.17	0.00
Locked	62.6	28.8	91.9	100.0

The overall particle size illustrates a P_{80} of around 250 μm ,

where chalcocopyrite is the coarsest among the copper minerals with a P_{80} of around 80-90 μm , similar to that of pyrite. Cuprite is considerably finer with a P_{80} of 40 μm and malachite, present in trace amounts, is finest with a P_{80} of 4-5 μm . Particle and grain size distribution is provided in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Particle and grain size distribution (TIMA image)

The TIMA image (Figure 5), which presents copper distribution, is based on exposed surface area and demonstrates the in-situ position of chalcocopyrite and cuprite. The image illustrates their association in complex particles as boundary controlled grains between plagioclase and K-feldspars. Although the leachability of the host grains is moderate, this grain boundary association may enhance accessibility of leach solutions to the copper mineral grains.

The TIMA results indicate also that the copper as cuprite could be leached relatively easily and, with its textural position at grain boundary, would provide some availability to in-situ grain positions.

The liberation characterisation based on the exposed surface area is presented in Table 4, where copper sulphides and oxides are grouped as suggested by Tonžetić (2015) into three categories: “60-100%”, “20-60%” and “<20%”.

Table 4. TIMA liberation characterization

Copper mineral groups and liberation category	Unit	Value
Cu Sulfide 60-100%	%	6.2
Cu Sulfide 20-60%	%	14.9
Cu Sulfide <20%	%	36.2
Cu Oxide 60-100%	%	23.2
Cu Oxide 20-60%	%	14.5
Cu Oxide <20%	%	4.90

As can be seen from Table 4, the distribution of copper based upon the exposed surface area shows that 21.1% of the copper as sulphides and around 37.7% of the copper as oxides can be classified as “liberated” and “middlings”. In aggregate, copper exposed to leach solutions and available to leaching is 58.8%.

Sequential Copper Assay

The stages of sequential copper assay were chosen based on the results from the mineralogical analysis provided in the previous section. The results of the sequential copper assay and calculated total copper are provided in Table 5.

Fig. 5. Copper distribution by copper species and exposed surface area of particle (TIMA image)

An estimation of copper minerals based on the sequential leaching are presented in Table 6.

Table 5. Sequential copper assay results

Leach Stage	Copper (%)
Acetic Acid Leach	0.05
Sulphuric Acid Leach	0.01
Cyanide Leach	0.02
Four-Acid Digestion	0.02
Total Copper, calculated	0.10

Table 6. Estimation of copper mineral groups

Copper Mineral Group	Copper Distribution (%)
Copper oxides	49.5
Chalcocite	10.3
Secondary Sulphides	20.6
Chalcopyrite	19.6
Total	100.0

The results from the sequential copper assay show that 49.5% of the copper is in copper oxides, 10.3% is in chalcocite, 20.6% is in secondary sulphides and 19.6% is in chalcopyrite.

As determined by sequential copper assays, approximately 59.8% of the copper contained in the samples is reported as acid soluble copper and it could be leached relatively easy.

Hydraulic Characterisation

To evaluate if the tailings material is suitable for leaching, the main hydraulic properties -like saturated hydraulic conductivity, compression and moisture retention capacity- were determined by GeoSystems Analysis Inc., using modified methods, originally developed for agricultural and engineered soils.

The saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}) of the material was found to be 1.5×10^{-5} cm/s. The value is consistent with those measured in similar tailings storage facilities (Aubertin et al, 2011, Adajar and Zarco, 2014). Based on the obtained K_{sat} results, the material has a mixed textural structure (clay loam, sandy clay loam or silty clay loam) and belongs to the moderate low permeability class.

The results from the 1-D consolidation test are summarised in Table 7.

Table 7. 1-D consolidation test results

Loading (pcf)	Compression (%)	Porosity (cm^3/cm^3)	Estimated tailings height (m)
100	0	0.485	0.3
1000	0.92	0.480	2.5
5000	2.2	0.473	12.6
10000	3.7	0.465	24.9

From the one-dimensional (1-D) consolidation test results, very little compression (max. 3.7%) was achieved and this may indicate small amounts of swelling clay. There is no significant reduction of porous space even at accumulation to a height of around 25 meters.

To define the ability of the tailings material to hold and release water, moisture retention curves (MRC) for MT-H sample and two sub-samples identified as MT-1 and MT-2 were experimentally constructed by GeoSystems Analysis Inc. The MRC curves, representing the volumetric water content versus soil water potential are shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. MRC curves (An unnamed SWRC software image)

As can be seen in Figure 6, the two tailing samples MT-H and MT-2 show strong water holding characteristics and this potentially will lead to the significant copper losses during the leaching. The coarse sample MT-1 shows typical coarse

texture water holding characteristics and similar to fine sand. The Moisture Retention Characteristic data could be used further to predict the flow behaviour and to quantify the leach solution that should be applied to fully contact the material.

Conclusions

A detailed mineralogical and hydraulic characterisation of the flotation tailings from historic Medet tailings dam were carried out to obtain data for further assessment and selection of the most efficient type of the leaching process for copper recovery. The most significant outcomes from the study are as follows:

- The assayed copper content of the tailings material is 0.105%. Copper content in the upper layers (3-3.5 m) of the tailings dam is 0.03% in average;
- With P_{80} of around 250 μm the material could be classified as fine grained;
- Copper is mainly present as cuprite (~43%) and chalcopyrite (~43%) with minor amounts of covellite (8.82%) and bornite (4.56%) and trace amounts of malachite (0.19%), chrysocolla (0.19%), chalcocite (0.10%) and tetrahedrite (0.07%);
- Given the amount of cuprite and other secondary copper minerals along with potential accessibility of leaching solution through grain boundary pathways and results from sequential copper assays, the tailings material indicates good leachability;
- With saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}) of 1.5×10^{-5} cm/s, the material has moderate to low permeability.

The successful application of a leaching process on the tailings material will depend mainly on the overall mineral abundance, mineral liberation characteristics, permeability and the amount of the small particle size fractions.

Further extensive and well planned metallurgical testwork to define copper extraction and acid consumption is required before the final decision on project feasibility.

References

- Adajar M. A., Zarco M., 2014. An empirical model for predicting hydraulic conductivity of mine tailings, *International Journal of GEOMATE*, 7, 1054-1061.
- ASTM D 2434 – 68. 2006. Standard Test Method for Permeability of Granular Soils (Constant Head), in: *Book of Standards Volume: 04.08 .6*
- ASTM D6836-16. 2016. Standard Test Methods for Determination of the Soil Water Characteristic Curve for Desorption Using Hanging Column, Pressure Extractor, Chilled Mirror Hygrometer or Centrifuge, in: *Book of Standards Volume: 04.09. 22*
- Aubertin M., Bussière B., Chapuis R., 2011. Hydraulic conductivity of homogenised tailings from hard rock mines, *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 33, 470-482.
- Babel B., Penz M., Schach E., Boehme S., Rudolph M., 2018. Reprocessing of a southern Chilean Zn tailing by flotation- A case study, *Minerals*, 8, 295.
- Dobrev T., Valchanova I., Stefanov Y., Magaeva S., 2009. Investigations of new anodic materials for zinc electrowinning, *Transactions of the Institute of Metal Finishing*, 87(3), 136-140.
- Figueiredo J., Vila M., Fiúza A., Góis J., Futuro A., Dinis M., Martins D., 2019. A holistic approach in re-mining old

- tailings deposits for the supply of critical-metals: A Portuguese case study, *Minerals*, 9, 638.
- Grigorova I., Dzhamyarov S., Nishkov I., 2015. Barite flotation concentrate from Kremikovtzi "black" tailings, *Journal of International Scientific Publications: Materials, Methods & Technologies*, 9, 561-577.
- Grigorova I., 2011. Gravitatsionni tehnologii pri upravlenie na minni odpadatsi. *Izd. Ritt, Silistra*. (in Bulgarian).
- Parkinson G. A., Bhappu R. B., 1995. The sequential copper analysis method – geological, mineralogical and metallurgical implications, *SME Pre-print*, 95-90.
- Schulz B., Sandmann D., Gilbricht S., 2020. SEM-based automated mineralogy and its application in geo- and material sciences, *Minerals*, 10 (11), 1004.
- Shengo M., Maloba B., 2013. Recovery of cobalt and copper through reprocessing of tailings from flotation of oxidised ores, *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 1085–1090.
- Stanković V., Milosevic V., Milicevic D., Gorgievski M., Bogdanovic G., 2018. Reprocessing of the old flotation tailings deposited on the RTB Bor tailings pond - a case study, *Chemical Industry and Chemical Engineering Quarterly*, 24 (4), 333-344.
- Sultanov A. , 2001. Geological Report, Results of the detailed exploration of the Medet tailings impoundment, 162.
- Tonžetić I. Ž., 2015. Quantitative analysis of iron ore using SEM-based technologies, in: *Iron Ore*, ed. L. Lu, Woodhead Publishing, 161-189.
- Valchanova I., Stefanov Y., Stefanov K., Tabakova N., Dobrev T., 2011. Blocking of harmful effect of bismuth ions during electroextraction of zinc from sulphate electrolytes, *Transactions of the Institute of Metal Finishing*, 89(4), 210-214.
- Yankova T., 2020. Mineral processing waste utilisation, *Proceedings of the XX International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference, Bulgaria*, 821-828.